

ROLADE TORN (TEMPE WITH SWEET CORN) AS HEALTHY FOOD INNOVATION TO OVERCOME LOW NUTRIENTS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

Rolade is a dish cooked in the form of a roll, typically made from a flat piece of meat that has high animal protein. However, in Indonesia, the consumption of animal protein is still low. The needs of rolade ingredients, which is meat, can not be used by middle to lower society. Due to its high price, we substitute the usage of meat in rolade with cheaper ingredients but the protein content not inferior to the meat, namely tempe. To make more nutritious, we added tempe rolade with sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*). This study aims to test the effect of sweet corn addition on tempe rolade with organoleptics test which include color, taste, aroma, texture and level of public acceptance. Furthermore, this study aims to provide innovative use of plant-based protein to foods. The method used is experiment by varying the addition of sweet corn, i.e., 15%, 30%, and 45%. Based on the results of the organoleptic test by 2 people nutritionists and 1 culinary expert showed that the A5 treatment (55:45) with sweet corn addition as much as 45% produced the color (gold), the taste (savory and sweeter), the aroma (savory) and the best texture (soft and solid). While the acceptability test results shows that the highest favorite value by hedonic scale is 3.95. Therefore, based on organoleptic results, the best composition of sweet corn added 45%. Therefore, tempe rolade with sweet corn addition in favor of affordable nutrients and overcome low nutrients to support Indonesia Emas 2030.

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1. Introduction

Protein is one source of an essential nutrient for the human body. Protein plays a very important to support the existence of every cell of the body. In addition, the protein has an important role in the formation of the immune system (immune system) is intended as an antibody, and also serves as a control system in the form of the hormone. Protein deficiency can cause diseases and deficiency balance. Protein is needed by the body as a builder substance, regulator and fuel. Sources of protein can be obtained from animal protein (meat 25-36%, 20-35% of fish, milk 3.20%) and vegetable (soy 36.49%, 21.22% Almond) [1]. One of animal proteins which are most favored by the people of Indonesia to eat is meat.

Figure 1. Structure of Protein [2]

Meat have a fairly high protein content and is required by the human body because the meat contains essential amino acids, vitamins, fats, and minerals. Many processed meat have made into food products. However, livestock products such as meat has the properties that are easily damaged. In order to overcome that problem, meat will require a good handling and processing. One of meat processing is to change the form of raw meat into processed form which has a longer shelf life with the taste, aroma, color, and shape to be more attractive appearance in accordance with the needs of consumers. One of the example of processed meat products is rolade.

Figure 2. Rolade Meat [3]

Rolade is made from a mixture of beef or chicken meat which is minced and mixed with starch or flour with or without the addition of other ingredients and seasonings that formed round [4]. Rolade become one of the meat-processing innovation that has high source of animal protein. However, the consumption of animal protein in Indonesia is still low. This is caused by the high price of animal protein, which is 120 thousand per kg [5]. If left unchecked, this will be a cause of malnutrition. One alternative to overcome this problem is to provide meat alternative with rolade basic materials which are not expensive but have no less nutritional content, i.e., such as soybeans. Soybean is one source of vegetable protein which is relatively cheap when compared to animal protein sources. Soybean selected as the raw material of nutritious food because it has a high nutritional content. In 100 grams of soy beans contains 20.00 g of water, 30.90 g protein, 15.10 g of fat, 30.10 g carbohydrates, 0.7 to 2.6 g ash and 268.00 kJ of energy

[6]. The protein requirement of 55 grams per day can be filled with foods derived from soybeans as much as 157.14 gram [7]. Ironically, one of processed soy products like tempe has not been much inovated as processed food material.

Tempe is made from boiled soybeans fermented by the fungus *Rhizopus Oligosporus*. During fermentation, the seeds of soybean trapped in knitted fungal mycelia form a compact solid white [8]. Tempe contains 20.8 grams of protein, 201 calories, 8.8 grams fat, 155 mg of calcium [9]. Soybean has been developed as tempe nuggets, soybean milk, chips, and crackers. tempe can be developed as an alternative material to substitute meat on rolade.

Rolade tempe are generally the same in the manufacturing process, the difference is the raw material of Rolade in general. The addition of certain ingredients in processed soybean rolade expected to improve the consistency of the nutritional value, taste, acidity and wetness control and implementing forms and shapes [10]. Rolade processed products from tempe are generally added various vegetables such as carrots, celery, broccoli. One of the vegetables that have not been tested in soybean rolade is processed sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*).

Sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) is classified based on its endosperm, where sweet corn endosperm has sugar content higher than the starch. The addition of sweet corn in this Rolade expected as additional material (filler) that serves binding emulsion stability, improve the water-binding power, improve taste, reduce shrinkage during processing and reduce production costs [11].

Figure 3. Sweet Corn [12]

The existence of this study aims to examine the effect of the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) to organoleptic which include color, flavor, aroma, texture and preference on rolade tempe. In addition, it aims to deliver innovation to the food use of vegetable protein rolade in the market. The benefits of this research are expected to provide a comparison between the composition of the base material with the appropriate filler and most appreciated by the public if using sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) on rolade tempe.

2. Research Methodology

The method used in this study is an experimental method by varying the composition of the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*), i.e., 15%, 30%, and 45%. Then conducted organoleptic evaluation of each additional sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*). This research was conducted 4 times repetitions of each sample were made. Data processed by One-Way

Analysis of Variance (One-Way ANOVA) to determine the effect of treatment. In order to know the difference between the treatment were used subsequent test, that is Duncan test. This study carried out for 4 months at Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

The tools used in this study are pots, stoves, spoons, knives, blenders, plates, scales, ovens, heating mantles, 1/2 kilo plastic. The ingredients used include soybean tempeh, sweet corn, water, eggs, vegetables, cooking oil, spring roll skin. Additional ingredients include fried shallots 1 tablespoon, finely chopped garlic 2 cloves, pepper, sugar, celery, salt, chili, cucumber.

Procedure of making rolade tempe was the first step, mix well tempe and sweet corn that has been mashed for 5 minutes, flour, fried shallots, egg white, and garlic until blended. Add salt, pepper powder, sugar and celery leaves and stir until completely flat. Next, wrap the mixture with aluminum foil to form a 3-inch diameter rice cake and tie the two ends together with rubber. Steam the mixture for 20 minutes over medium heat until cooked. chill, then cut into pieces 1.5 centimeters thick. After that dip the rolade into the coating material, then fry it in oil which is hot enough over medium heat until cooked.

Observations were made on the experimental results of making tempe rollers with various compositions that have been determined between the comparison of the composition of tempeh and corn. Observations were carried out organoleptically such as observing color, taste, aroma, and texture by experts. Experts are permitted to fill out questionnaires that have been made by researchers in accordance with your objective assessment.

There are 3 experts who will conduct an organoleptic test on the experimental results of making rolade. Three of them were Mr. Alsuendra (IPB alumni) and Mrs. Irida (alumni of malaysia) and 1 expert cookery, that is Mrs. Sachriani (Head of Vocational Education Culinary Arts). Each of the experts will conduct an organoleptic test on 4 treatments of tempe rollers samples that have been made, namely A_0 (100: 0), A_1 (85:15), A_3 (70:30), and A_5 (55:45).

The acceptance level test aims to test preferences and find out what some of the students of Universitas Negeri Jakarta (consumers) about food products rolade tempe which inovated with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) before commercialized in the market (large scale). The results of this analysis are expected to be a benchmark for manufacturers to create and develop innovative products with the addition of corn for Rolade tempe accordingly. Thus, the product can be obtained in accordance with the public interest.

The acceptance level test conducted by 70 undergraduate student from Universitas Negeri Jakarta were taken at random in each faculty. The panelists were given a technical briefing on questionnaires to answer the grading scale hedonic 6. After that, each panelist will test the level of acceptance of rolade tempe with a variety of comparisons between soybean and sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by observing the color and texture, aroma perceived by the sense of smell, and taste to know the taste of rolade tempe.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Organoleptic test by experts

Based on the observations of three experts according to their respective fields. Three of them were Mr. Alshendra (IPB alumni) and Mrs. Irda (alumni of Malaysia) and 1 expert cookery, that is Mrs. Sachriani (Head of Vocational Education Culinary Arts). After the experiment of making tempe Rolade with 4 treatment samples with a ratio of soybean and corn ie A_1 sample treatment (85:15), A_3 (70:30), A_5 (55:45), and A_0 (Control or without the addition of corn), then obtained results as follows.

Table 1. Appearance Test Results Rolade Tempe by Experts

Test	sample treatment			
	A_0	A_1	A_3	A_5
Color	Chocolate	Pale brown	Chocolate	Golden
Flavor	Not savory	Less savory and less sweet	Savory and sweet	Savory and sweeter
Aroma	Dreadful	Dreadful	Savory	Savory
Texture	Not dense	Less tender and softer	Soft and less dense	Soft and dense

Table 1. states that rolade tempe on the sample A_1 (85:15) as a pale brown color influenced by the results comparison of soybean with corn as corn less than tempe, savory and sweet tastes less sweet, less pleasant aroma, and less tender texture. Sample A_3 (70:30) produce a brown color after fried, savory and sweet taste is due to comparison of soybean with corn more than the samples A_1 , has savory aroma, the texture is soft and less dense. Samples A_5 (55:45) produces a golden brown color after fried, has savory and sweet taste due to the number of comparisons tempe with more corn than the samples A_3 , has savory aroma, also the texture is soft and dense. Samples A_0 (Control or without the addition of corn) produces brown color, savory taste just like savory tempe mixed with spices that have been stirred, savory aroma typical of tempe and dense texture.

Figure 4 Rolade Tempe with Sweet Corn

3.2. Panelist

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Rate on test acceptance level has four indicator with four treatment samples. Four indicators include color, flavor, aroma, and texture. Four treatment samples by varying the amount of the composition of tempe and sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) that A₀ (100: 0), A₁ (85:15), A₃ (70:30), and A₅ (55:45).

3.2.1. Effect of Treatment of Rolade Tempe Color

Rolade color reception level value of tempe with various treatments the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Acceptance Level Test Results Color Rolade Tempe

Sample Treatment	Numerical Scale Color	Hedonic Scale
A ₀	2,06a	Somewhat like
A ₁	2,97ab	Somewhat like
A ₃	3,87b	Like
A ₅	4,14bc	Really like

Description: The small letters indicate significantly different.

Based on table 2. can be explained that the test results of product acceptance rate rolade tempe color by the addition of corn between 2.06 to 4.14. Based on the values obtained showed that the level of consumer acceptance of these products were well received. However, the A₅ treatment, the addition of corn (55:45) shows the level of acceptance of better color. The resulting color is preferred by consumers. Meanwhile, in treatment A₁ (85:15) very small degree of consumer acceptance.

At the reception level test rolade for tempe color can be concluded that the value of the numerical scale of the most preferred color was 4.14 (very fancy) on A₅ treatment with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45% because of all the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) significantly different from each other.

3.2.2. Effect of Treatment of Rolade Tempe Taste

Value acceptance rate rolade tempe flavor with various treatments the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) can be seen in Table 3

Table 3. Test Results of Acceptance Taste Rate for Rolade Tempe

Sample Treatment	Numerical Scale Sense	Hedonic Scale
A ₀	2,04a	Somewhat like
A ₁	2,99ab	Somewhat like
A ₃	3,57b	Like
A ₅	3,96bc	Like

Description: The small letters indicate significantly different.

Data in Table 3. indicates that the test results of product acceptance rate of rolade tempe flavor by the addition of corn ranged from 2.04 to 3.96. Treatment A₅ (55:45) shows the degree of consumer acceptance is the greatest of the product's taste. The addition of corn as much as 45% rated the most optimal give a sense of the most preferred by consumers because of the many corn added results tempe rolade sweeter. While treatment A₀ (control) the level of acceptance of the resulting flavor is very low.

At the reception level test rolade flavor tempe can be concluded that the value of the numerical scale of the most preferred color was 3.96 (Really like) on A₅ treatment with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45% because of all the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) significantly different from each other.

3.2.3. Effect of Treatment of Rolade Tempe Aroma

The value of acceptance rate for aroma with various treatments can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Aroma Acceptance Rate Test Results of Rolade Tempe

Treatment	Numerical Scale Aroma	Hedonic Scale
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A0	2,17a	Somewhat like
A1	3,14ab	Like
A3	3,54b	Like
A5	3,76b	Like

Description: The small letters indicate significantly different.

Data in Table 4. indicates that the test results of product acceptance rate for rolade tempe aroma by adding corn ranged from 2.17 to 3.76. A₅ treatment by the addition of corn by 45% shows the level of consumer acceptance on the aroma of the product is the nicest. The addition of corn as much as 45% rated gives the most optimal flavor and the most preferred by consumers. While treatment A₀ (control) the level of acceptance aroma of rolade tempe is very low. At the acceptance level test for rolade tempe aroma can be concluded that the most preferred color was 3.76 (Really Like) on A₅ treatment with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45% because of all the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) significantly different from each other, except in treatment A₃ (70:30) and A₅ (55:45).

3.2.4. Effect of Treatment of Rolade Tempe Texture

Value acceptance rate of rolade tempe texture with a variety of sweet corn addition can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Texture Acceptance Rate Test Results of Rolade tempe

Treatment	Numerical Scale Texture	Hedonic Scale
A0	2,09a	Somewhat like
A1	3,00ab	Like
A3	3,59b	Like
A5	3,96bc	Like

Description: The small letters indicate significantly different.

Data in Table 5. indicates that the test results of product acceptance rate of rolade tempe texture by adding sweet corn ranged from 2.09 to 3.96. A₅ treatment by the addition of corn by 45% shows the nicest level of consumer acceptance on the texture of the product. The addition

of corn as much as 45% gives the most optimal texture to the most preferred by consumers. While treatment A₀ (control) the level of acceptance of texture rolade tempe produced is very low. At the reception level test rolade texture of tempe can be concluded that the most preferred color was 3.96 (Really Like) on A₅ treatment with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45% because of all the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) significantly different from each other.

3.2.5 Effect of Treatment for Rolade Tempe Total Acceptance Rate

The value of total acceptance rate of rolade tempe with various sweet corn addition can be seen in Table 6

Table 6. Level Test Results of Total Revenue to Rolade Tempe

Treatment	Numerical Scale Texture	Hedonic Scale
A0	2,09a	Somewhat like
A1	3,02ab	Like
A3	3,64b	Like
A5	3,95bc	Like

Description: The small letters indicate significantly different.

Data in Table 6. indicates that the test results from the total acceptance rate rolade tempe product by the addition of corn ranged from 2.09 to 3.95 (somewhat like - really like). Based on the results of statistical test by analysis of variance, the results show that the use of various compositions of the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) on Rolade tempe has significant effect on total acceptance rate of Rolade tempe. Total acceptance rate include four types of assessments done of which include color, flavor, aroma, and texture of the product. The fourth component of the acceptance assessment for Rolade tempe on different levels of addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) were significantly different. The value of the acceptance rate for rolade tempe produced the most preferred color was 4.14 (like) in the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45%. Numerical scale value most preferred flavor was 3.96 (Like) in the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45%. The most preferred aroma is 3.76 (Like) in the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45%. The value for most preferred texture was 3.96 (Like) in the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) by 45%. The above results show that the level of total acceptance rate of Rolade tempe composition with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) is 45% produced the highest preference level with the value of 3.95 (Really Like) on A₅ treatment.

4. Conclusion

Based on this research can be concluded that the analysis of variance (One-Way Anova) F count > F table and significant 0.000 < 0.05, as well as Duncan test showed that there was significantly different from the range for each composition the addition of sweet corn (*Zea*

Saccharata mays). The addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) with varying composition affect the organoleptic ie color, flavor, aroma, texture, and the level of acceptance on Rolade tempe produced. Treatment A5 (55:45) with the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) of 45% produces color (Golden), taste (savory and sweet), Aroma (Tuberose), and texture (Soft and solid) were most preferred and has the highest value with hedonic scale like (3.95). Therefore, based on the organoleptic test, the recommended composition of the addition of sweet corn (*Zea Mays Saccharata*) according to the level of consumer acceptance is 45%.

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